

Synthesis and characterization of UO_2^{2+} , ZrO^{2+} and Th^{4+} complexes with 3-(*p*-substituted aryl)-2-thiohydantoin

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Abstract : A few complexes of the type $[\text{ML}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and $[\text{ThL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$, where $\text{M}=\text{UO}_2^{2+}$ and ZrO^{2+} ; $\text{HL} = 3$ -benzylideneimino-2-thiohydantoin, 3-*p*-nitrobenzylideneimino-2-thiohydantoin, 3-*p*-methoxybenzylideneimino-2-thiohydantoin, 3-*p*-chlorobenzylideneimino-2-thiohydantoin have been synthesized and characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, thermal analysis, conductance, magnetic moment studies and spectroscopic data (^1H NMR, IR and electronic). The results indicate that the complexes of UO_2^{2+} and ZrO^{2+} are hexacoordinated where as those of Th^{4+} ions are octacoordinated.

Keywords : 3-Substituted thiohydantoin, UO_2^{2+} , ZrO^{2+} , Th^{4+} .

Introduction

3-Substituted-2-thiohydantoin (Fig. 1) such as 3-benzylideneimino-2-thiohydantoin (Hbit), 3-*p*-methoxybenzylideneimino-2-thiohydantoin (Hmbit), 3-*p*-nitrobenzylideneimino-2-thiohydantoin (Hnbit) and 3-*p*-chlorobenzylideneimino-2-thiohydantoin (Hcbit) are reported to be bioactive^{1,2}. They have multicoordination sites such as azomethine nitrogen, thiocarbonyl sulphur, imino nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen, but their coordination chemistry with UO_2^{2+} , ZrO^{2+} and Th^{4+} has not been studied as yet. Hence, as a part of our study on the complexes with bioactive ligands containing NOS donors³, we report here a synthesis and characterization of a few complexes of the title ligands with UO_2^{2+} , ZrO^{2+} and Th^{4+} ions.

R = Phenyl, *p*-methoxyphenyl, *p*-nitrophenyl, *p*-chlorophenyl

Fig. 1

Results and discussion

The analytical data indicate 2 : 1 (L : M) stoichiometry for all the complexes (Table 1). These are coloured

and decompose without melting above 250 °C. All are insoluble in water and most of the common organic solvents but slightly soluble in DMSO and DMF. Low molar conductance values ($20\text{--}30 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) in DMSO indicate them to be non-electrolytes. However, the conductivity value is higher than as expected for non-electrolytes probably due to partial solvolysis of the complexes in DMSO medium⁴.

The characteristic IR bands observed in the spectra of the ligands at ~ 3400 , ~ 1450 , ~ 1320 , ~ 1080 and $\sim 840 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to $\nu\text{N-H}$, thioimide-I, -II, -III and -IV bands respectively⁵. The positions of all these bands remain practically unaltered in the present complexes implying non-coordination of thioimido sulphur or nitrogen atoms to metal ions. The band at $\sim 1710 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to carbonyl $\nu\text{C=O}$ of the ligand is found to be absent and two new bands of medium intensity are observed at ~ 1580 and $\sim 1520 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to $\nu\text{C}\equiv\text{C}$ and $\nu\text{C}\equiv\text{O}$ respectively indicating that the ligand coordinates to the metal ions through deprotonation of enolic OH after enolisation^{6,7}. The band observed at 1640 cm^{-1} due to azomethine $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ of the ligand is lowered by $10\text{--}20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in this complexes implying coordination of azomethine nitrogen to the metal ion. Consequently, the band occurring at 1040 cm^{-1} due to $\nu\text{N-N}$ of the ligand is blue shifted to $\sim 1060 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes suggesting there by reduction of the repulsion between the lone pair of electrons on N atoms owing to coordination via azomethine nitrogen atom.

Table 1. Analytical data of complexes

Complexes (Colour)	% of Metal		% of C		% of N		% of S		% of H	
	Found	(Calcd.)	Found	(Calcd.)	Found	(Calcd.)	Found	(Calcd.)	Found	(Calcd.)
UO ₂ (bit) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ (Brown)	32.01 (32.07)		32.23 (32.34)		11.26 (11.32)		8.57 (8.62)		2.64 (2.69)	
UO ₂ (mbit) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ (Steel grey)	29.59 (29.67)		32.20 (32.90)		10.38 (10.47)		7.93 (7.98)		2.89 (2.99)	
UO ₂ (nbit) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ (Light brown)	28.53 (28.62)		28.72 (28.84)		13.41 (13.46)		7.62 (7.69)		2.10 (2.16)	
UO ₂ (cbit) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ (Yellowish white)	29.21 (29.34)		29.47 (29.59)		10.31 (10.35)		7.83 (7.89)		2.19 (2.21)	
ZrO(bit) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ (Grey)	15.85 (15.91)		41.36 (41.43)		14.43 (14.50)		10.09 (11.02)		3.41 (3.45)	
ZrO(mbit) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ (Dull yellow)	14.14 (14.26)		41.26 (41.30)		13.10 (13.14)		9.08 (10.01)		3.71 (3.75)	
ZrO(nbit) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ (Straw yellow)	13.56 (13.62)		35.79 (35.86)		16.62 (16.73)		9.47 (9.56)		2.62 (2.68)	
ZrO(cbit) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ (Greyish white)	14.01 (14.06)		36.07 (37.02)		12.91 (12.96)		9.82 (9.87)		2.73 (2.77)	
Th(bit) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ (Yellowish brown)	27.09 (28.01)		28.87 (28.98)		13.47 (13.52)		7.67 (7.72)		2.37 (2.41)	
Th(mbit) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ (Brownish yellow)	26.09 (26.12)		29.67 (29.72)		12.58 (12.61)		7.17 (7.20)		2.67 (2.70)	
Th(nbit) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ (Canary yellow)	25.16 (25.27)		26.09 (26.14)		15.21 (15.25)		6.86 (6.97)		1.94 (1.96)	
Th(cbit) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ (Chocolate)	25.77 (25.86)		26.71 (26.75)		12.43 (12.48)		7.04 (7.09)		1.98 (2.01)	

The IR spectra of nitrate complexes of Th⁴⁺ show additional band at ~1390 and ~1020 cm⁻¹ which unambiguously suggest the presence of coordinated nitrate anions in unidentate manner corresponding to ν_2 , ν_4 mode of vibration of coordinated nitrate ion under C_{2v} symmetry⁸. The presence of nitrate ion in the coordination sphere in Th^{IV} complexes has also been supported by non-electrolytic nature of complex in DMSO. Besides, the bands observed at ~3500(s), ~1600(s), ~880(m) cm⁻¹ may assigned to $\nu(\text{OH})$, $\delta(\text{OH})$ and $\rho(r)$ of coordinated water⁹, which is further confirmed by thermal analysis. The occurrence of new bands at ~530–515 and ~460–450 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes further suggest the coordination of metal ions through oxygen and nitrogen respectively¹⁰. The uranyl complexes exhibit a strong band at ~940–900 cm⁻¹ and the medium intensity band at ~835–820 cm⁻¹ assignable to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ mode respectively¹¹. The zirconyl complexes exhibit one strong band in the region

900–870 cm⁻¹ which can be attributed to the $\nu(\text{Zr}=\text{O})$ as reported earlier¹² indicating the presence of $(\text{Zr}=\text{O})^{2+}$ moiety in these complexes.

Thermal studies : The complexes remain almost stable upto ~150 °C and thereafter a slight depression upto ~190 °C are observed. This weight loss correspond to loss of two water molecules indicating them to be coordinated water in conformity with our earlier observation from analytical and IR spectral investigations. The anhydrous complexes remain stable upto ~330–430 °C and thereafter the complexes show rapid degradation presumably due to decomposition of organic constituents of the complex molecules as indicated by the steep fall in the percentage weight loss. The decomposition continues upto ~540 °C and reaches to a stable product in each complex as indicated by the consistency in weight in the plateau of the thermogram. This corresponds to the composition of their stable oxides. The decomposition temperature varies for different complexes as shown is Table 2.

Thermal stability of such complexes is found to be in the following order : (bit) complexes : $\text{UO}_2^{2+} < \text{ZrO}^{2+} < \text{Th}^{4+}$; (mbit) complexes : $\text{ZrO}^{2+} < \text{UO}_2^{2+} < \text{Th}^{4+}$; (nbit) complexes : $\text{Th}^{4+} < \text{ZrO}^{2+} < \text{UO}_2^{2+}$; (cbit) complexes : $\text{ZrO}^{2+} < \text{Th}^{4+} < \text{UO}_2^{2+}$.

Spectral studies : The present system of ligands like Hbit, Hmbit, Hnbit, Hcbit where 2-thiohydantoin is coupled at its 3-position with benzylidene, *p*-methoxybenzylidene, *p*-nitrobenzylidene respectively display only two bands corresponding to λ_{max} , 250–270 and 320–330 nm assignable to $\Pi\text{-}\Pi^*$ and $n\text{-}\Pi^*$ transition respectively indicating extensive conjugation. However, the presence of O-CH₃, chloro and nitro substituents in *p*-position of benzylidene system does not produce appreciable effect as far as λ_{max} is concerned.

The spectra of UO_2^{2+} complexes display mainly one weak band at 440 nm and a highly intense band in the range 280–290 nm, which may be due to $^1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow ^3\Pi_u$ transition and charge transfer transition respectively¹¹. It may be noted that the band occurring at 370 nm due to uranyl moiety because of apical oxygen $\rightarrow f^o(U)$ transition¹² is being merged with the ligand band due to $n\text{-}\Pi^*$ transition as evident from broadness and intensity. The electronic spectra of Th^{IV} and ZrO^{2+} complexes exhibit only highly intensive additional band in the region 400–430 nm which may be due to charge transfer besides the ligand bands.

The ¹H NMR spectra of the ligands and complexes are recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ : CDCl₃ medium. The ¹H NMR spectra of the ligands show a complex broad multiplet at δ 7.2–7.9 ppm corresponding to five aromatic protons for Hbit and four aromatic protons for other ligands due to phenyl group. The singlet at $\sim\delta$ 9.4 ppm, the triplet at $\sim\delta$ 9.1 and doublet at $\sim\delta$ 3.42 ppm may be assigned due to N=C-H proton, -NH proton, and -CH₂ protons respectively. Hmbit shows an additional peak due to -CH₃O proton at $\sim\delta$ 4.7 ppm.

The signal due to H-C=N proton shows a upfield shift by δ 0.2–0.4 ppm indicating coordination of azomethine nitrogen. The proton signal due to -CH₂ proton in the ligand corresponds to single proton being unaltered in its position there by indicating involvement of one hydrogen atom of CH₂ group in enolisation through tautomerism. However the positions of other bands don't change appreciably because of the coordination of the ligand with metal ions. Only the triplet due to NH proton of the ligand becomes doublet in the present complexes supporting our earlier observation. Besides an additional

peak at $\sim\delta$ 3.6 ppm is observed in all the complexes indicating the presence of coordinated water molecules.

From the results of the above studies, the following tentative structures (Fig. 2) have been assigned for the present complexes.

Fig. 2

Experimental

Reagent grade chemicals were used in the present study. The ligands (HL) such as Hbit, Hnbit, Hmbit and Hcbit were prepared adopting literature methods¹³ by condensing thiosemicarbazones of benzaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde, *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde respectively with monochloro acetic acid in dry pyridine. They were recrystallized from ethanol and their purity was checked by elemental analyses.

Preparation of the complexes of the type $[\text{M}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and $[\text{ThL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$; $M = \text{UO}_2^{2+}$ and ZrO^{2+} : A hot ethanolic solution of the ligand (HL) was treated with aqueous solution of the corresponding hydrated $\text{UO}_2^{2+}/\text{ZrO}^{2+}/\text{Th}^{IV}$ nitrates in 2 : 1 molar ratio and the pH of the resulting solution was adjusted to 8–8.5 by adding NaOH. Coloured complex, which precipitated out immediately in each case was filtered, washed several times with water and finally with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo* over fused CaCl₂.

Uranium, thorium and zirconium are estimated as U₃O₈, ZrO₂ and ThO₂ respectively by standard methods¹³. C, H and N contents were determined by microanalysis using MLW-CHN micro analyzer, whereas sulphur content was estimated as a BaSO₄¹³. Room temperature magnetic susceptibilities were measured by Gouy method¹⁴ which indicate the complexes to be diamagnetic. The molar conductance measurements were car-

Table 2. Thermal analysis of complexes of the type $ML_2(H_2O)_2$ and $ThL_2(H_2O)_2(NO_3)_2$; HL = Hbit, Hmbit, Hnbit, Hcbit, M = UO_2^{2+} , ZrO^{2+}

Complexes	Total wt. for T_g (mg)	Temperature range of water loss	% of water loss Found (Calcd.)	Decomposition temp. ($^{\circ}C$)	% wt of residue Found (Calcd.)	Composition of the residue
$UO_2(\text{bit})_2(H_2O)_2$	102	130–180	4.81 (4.85)	~ 330 to ~ 540	37.79 (37.82)	U_3O_8
$ZrO(\text{bit})_2(H_2O)_2$	105	140–190	6.17 (6.21)	~ 395 to ~ 543	21.22 (21.27)	ZrO_2
$Th(\text{bit})_2(H_2O)_2(NO_3)_2$	126	140–200	4.29 (4.34)	~ 410 to ~ 547	31.79 (31.88)	ThO_2
$ZrO(\text{mbit})_2(H_2O)_2$	103	130–190	5.59 (5.63)	~ 340 to ~ 542	19.21 (19.27)	ZrO_2
$UO_2(\text{mbit})_2(H_2O)_2$	106	130–200	4.41 (4.48)	~ 385 to ~ 546	52.41 (52.49)	U_3O_8
$Th(\text{mbit})_2(H_2O)_2(NO_3)_2$	87	140–210	4.01 (4.05)	~ 400 to ~ 547	29.67 (29.72)	ThO_2
$Th(\text{nbit})_2(H_2O)_2(NO_3)_2$	108	140–180	3.89 (3.92)	~ 350 to ~ 540	28.69 (28.75)	ThO_2
$ZrO(\text{nbit})_2(H_2O)_2$	112	135–190	5.32 (5.37)	~ 380 to ~ 542	18.37 (18.41)	ZrO_2
$UO_2(\text{nbit})_2(H_2O)_2$	104	130–200	4.29 (4.32)	~ 385 to ~ 542	33.67 (33.73)	U_3O_8
$ZrO(\text{cbit})_2(H_2O)_2$	116	130–190	5.49 (5.55)	~ 340 to ~ 538	18.96 (19.00)	ZrO_2
$Th(\text{cbit})_2(H_2O)_2(NO_3)_2$	112	140–190	3.97 (4.01)	~ 375 to ~ 535	29.37 (29.43)	ThO_2
$UO_2(\text{cbit})_2(H_2O)_2$	109	140–210	4.39 (4.43)	~ 390 to ~ 540	34.54 (34.60)	U_3O_8

ried out at room temperature with a Toshniwal conductivity Bridge (Model CL-01-06, cell constant 0.5 cm^{-1}) using $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ solution of the complexes in DMSO. FTIR spectra in KBr pellets were recorded on a Varian FTIR spectrophotometer, Australia. The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Thermogravimetric analysis was done by Netzch-429 thermoanalyser simultaneously recording of TG and DT curves at a rate of $10 \text{ }^{\circ}C \text{ min}^{-1}$ in air. Around 50–100 mg of the sample was used in each case. The ^1H NMR spectra of the complexes were recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ medium on JEOL GSX-400 model equipment.

Purity of these complexes were established by TLC on silica gel. The colour, magnetic moment and analytical data of the complexes are summarized in Table 1.

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